

Harmonizing Neurology: Exploring Mindful Interventions for Healing and Well-Being

Abstract:

A growing body of scientific research is indicating the potential benefits of meditative- and mindfulness-focused interventions in ameliorating neuropsychiatric symptoms commonly associated with various neurological disorders. This article initiates by establishing precise definitions for meditation and mindfulness, followed by a concise exploration of the neurobiological mechanisms implicated in these interventions. Subsequently, a comprehensive array of meditative- and mindfulness-focused interventions is meticulously delineated, accompanied by their corresponding substantiating evidence in the context of mitigating neuropsychiatric symptoms within neurological conditions such as headaches, movement disorders, and chronic pain. The cumulative effect of these interventions underscores their viability for deeper scrutiny among individuals afflicted by neurological conditions.

Recommendations for healthcare professionals to prescribe these interventions necessitate a judicious consideration of both structural factors like insurance reimbursement and individual patient attributes such as their capacity to engage in group-based interventions.

Keywords:

Meditation - Mindfulness - Mind-Body – Neurology

In recent decades, the appeal of mind-body interventions (MBIs) has surged within both healthy and clinical populations in the United States. MBIs encompass a spectrum of therapies that revolve around leveraging the intricate interplay between the brain, mind, body, and behaviors to enhance overall health and well-being. [1] Common MBIs encompass practices like meditation-based programs, the cultivation of mindful awareness, relaxation techniques (such as Guided

Imagery and Progressive Muscle Relaxation), Yoga, and Tai Chi. While these techniques often draw from ancient traditions, many have been adapted for medical contexts while retaining their secular nature. The mounting body of evidence suggests that these interventions exhibit a reasonable safety profile [2] and exhibit potential in alleviating physical and emotional symptoms frequently associated with neurological disorders.

MBIs embody a multifaceted approach that amalgamates diverse strategies encompassing both mental and physical dimensions (e.g., breathe awareness, movement, meditation, mindfulness). Within this narrative review, our primary focus revolves around MBIs infused with meditative or mindfulness elements. Encompassing an exhaustive overview of all meditative- and mindfulness-centric interventions falls beyond the scope of this article. Instead, we concentrate on specific therapeutic avenues exhibiting promise within the realm of neurology. Precisely, we will (1) delineate the concepts of meditation and mindfulness; (2) provide a synopsis of chosen therapies integrating meditative or mindfulness facets; (3) scrutinize the evidence underpinning these therapies concerning neurological disorders and prevailing neuropsychiatric symptoms; and (4) underscore pertinent structural and patient-related factors that play a pivotal role in selecting appropriate candidates for these therapeutic modalities.

Exploring the essence and tenets of meditation and mindfulness:

Meditation constitutes a cluster of cognitive practices directed at skillfully regulating attention, moment by moment, onto a chosen focal point of awareness. The overarching objective is to cultivate a range of mental states, including emotional equilibrium and overall well-being. [3] The particular style of meditation employed hinges upon the specific object of focus. This may encompass interceptive sensations such as breath or body parts, mental imagery coupled with phrases (referred to as mantra), or even external entities like a flickering flame. These meditation

practices might involve maintaining unwavering attention on a solitary object (referred to as focused attention), transitioning focus between multiple objects, or engaging in an unswerving observation of momentary experiences devoid of a designated focal point (referred to as open monitoring). Moreover, these practices can be executed while seated or even in conjunction with bodily movements.

Distinctive variants of meditation, such as focused attention and open monitoring, are harnessed to foster mindfulness. Within the context of numerous Mind-Body Interventions (MBIs), mindfulness emerges as a pivotal component. This encompasses the deliberate regulation of attention towards present-moment encounters, infused with an attitude characterized by receptivity, inquisitiveness, and non-judgmental acceptance. [4] The deliberate regulation of attention pertains to the conscious direction of focus towards immediate internal facets (such as thoughts, emotions and bodily sensations) or external environmental elements. These facets are approached without entailing cognitive elaboration or evaluative judgments, regardless of their inherent positivity or desirability. This construct of mindfulness is conceived both as a dynamic state—actively engaging with the current moment [5]—and as a dispositional trait—a proclivity for mindfulness in daily existence. Elevated levels of both state and trait mindfulness correlate with diminished occurrences of emotional and physical symptoms. [6] A spectrum of interventions and methodologies have demonstrated efficacy in augmenting both the state and trait facets of mindfulness. These encompass interventions rooted in mindfulness, yoga, Tai chi, and other psychological modalities with a mindfulness emphasis (such as acceptance and commitment therapy). [7] Mindfulness-based interventions harness diverse meditation techniques (like focused attention and open monitoring) to nurture mindfulness. In each instance,

the shared element involves skillfully regulating attention towards immediate experiences, underscored by an attitude of receptive curiosity and impartiality.

Mindfulness often stands in juxtaposition to automaticity—an automatic response devoid of explicit intention. [8] It is widely acknowledged that responding habitually and automatically to internal discomfort (like thoughts, emotions, and bodily sensations can yield unfavorable outcomes.)

In fact, automatic reactions can spur endeavors to evade, suppress, or alter such internal discomfort, inadvertently intensifying or perpetuating these experiences and amplifying emotional or physical distress. [9] Consequently, interventions that prioritize mindfulness facilitate a transformation in an individual's rapport with challenging internal experiences. Concretely, mindfulness fosters a sense of detachment rather than an excessive identification with thoughts, emotions, and bodily sensations—termed as "decentering." [10] This reconfiguration disentangles the nexus between internal experiences and subsequent behaviors (like an urge to evade and ensuing avoidance), allowing individuals to opt for more adaptive responses. [11]

The Neuroscientific Underpinnings of Mindfulness: Unveiling the Brain's Response:

Neurobiological frameworks pertaining to mindfulness propose that the practice of mindfulness potentially elicits its effects through both structural and functional alterations within brain regions and networks that play pivotal roles in governing attention regulation, emotional regulation, and self-perspective and self-awareness. [12] Notably, mindfulness interventions have exhibited the capacity to enhance diverse aspects of attention (including selective and

executive attention), positioning Mind-Body Interventions (MBIs) as potent means of reshaping brain function—underscoring the reciprocal nature of brain-behavior interplay.

Neuroimaging investigations have pinpointed mindfulness meditation as a catalyst for functional modifications within the Cognitive Control Network, particularly in areas like the Anterior Cingulate Cortex (ACC), acknowledged for its contribution to attention and conflict resolution, and the dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex (PFC), a linchpin for executive functions. Additionally, mindfulness practice might also induce structural adaptations within the ACC.

Furthermore, compelling evidence underscores that mindfulness interventions wield a constructive influence on diverse facets of emotion regulation. [13] Neuroimaging inquiries intimate that functional alterations could vary contingent on the practitioner's level of experience in neophytes, mindfulness engagement may correspond with heightened activation within PFC regions and reduced amygdala activation in response to emotionally charged cues—an indicative manifestation of top-down regulatory mechanisms. [14] On the contrary, prolonged engagement with mindfulness might align with bottom-up strategies of emotion regulation, characterized by diminished emotional reactivity devoid of concurrent PFC activation—a phenomenon witnessed in more advanced practitioners.

Mindfulness exercises a transformative effect on various dimensions of self-perspective, including the profound concept of decentering—a practice involving the detachment from one's thoughts—and self-awareness, encompassing the discernment and assessment of internal physiological cues. [15] Profound insights from neuroimaging inquiries have illuminated the attenuation in the activity and connectivity of the default mode network (inclusive of cortical midline structures) among practitioners of mindfulness—this network is believed to govern processes related to self-referential thought patterns. The decrement in default mode network

activity aligns with a reduction in negative self-referential processing, exemplified by tendencies like rumination, apprehension, and self-critique. [16] Additionally, research has spotlighted structural alterations within brain regions intricately linked with the experience of selfhood, exemplified by the posterior cingulate cortex and the insula—both of which have displayed discernible changes. [17]

Enhancing well-being: Interventions rooted in mindfulness:

Mindfulness principles and practices, initially derived from Buddhism, were skillfully reshaped by Jon Kabat-Zinn, rendering them secular and conveniently tailored for integration into clinical contexts. [18] These "mindfulness-based" interventions accentuate the significance of mindfulness meditation and infuse mindfulness principles into a diverse array of activities.

Among the prominent iterations, two stand out: Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) and Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT). [19] MBSR, originally crafted to alleviate the distress of patients grappling with chronic pain unresponsive to conventional treatments has subsequently exhibited the potential to ameliorate symptoms of depression and anxiety not only within the chronic pain demographic but also among broader community samples—a testament reaffirmed by meta-analyses. [20] MBCT, an offshoot of MBSR, was adapted with the intention of curbing the recurrence of depression among individuals contending with repetitive depressive episodes. This variant assimilates more cognitive therapy elements that align with the contours of ruminative depressive thought processes. MBCT, too, has permeated a diverse spectrum of neuropsychiatric domains such as anxiety and chronic pain.

An array of other mindfulness-based interventions have been crafted for specific cohorts or conditions—an example being Mindfulness-Oriented Recovery Enhancement devised to address chronic pain. [21] The majority of these interventions find their roots in either MBSR or MBCT.

Typically, mindfulness interventions transpire within a group setting, extending over the course of eight weekly sessions, each spanning 1 to 2 hours, supplemented by daily home practice, and occasionally featuring a retreat day. Each session encompasses a blend of meditative exercises, group discussions and explorations, as well as didactic elements. Formal elements like meditation and yoga, alongside informal practices like mindful walking and eating, synergistically equip participants with the skills to foster mindfulness in their daily lives.

Intelligent initiatives: The evolution of smart programs

For more than four decades, the Benson–Henry Institute for Mind Body Medicine has spearheaded the investigation of Mind-Body Interventions (MBIs) based on the pioneering groundwork laid by Dr. Herbert Benson. This research has centered around the formulation of the "relaxation response," a concept considered to be the physiological antithesis of the Fight/flight response. The roots of this endeavor trace back to meditative practices characterized by the rhythmic repetition of a word or short phrase synchronized with the breath. A cornerstone of these practices involves passive acknowledgment of distracting thoughts, followed by the re-centering of attention on the breath. The trajectory of this focused awareness practice has evolved to encompass an extensive repertoire of cognitive and physical techniques, collectively referred to as the "SMART program"—an acronym signifying Stress Management and Resiliency Training. This comprehensive initiative encompasses several facets including relaxation response training, heightened stress awareness, and cognitive strategies for managing stress. [22] Furthermore, the SMART program introduces a diverse spectrum of approaches aimed at enhancing resilience, spanning positive psychology, the cultivation of acceptance, social support, nurturing pro-social behaviors, fostering spiritual connections, and advocating a healthy lifestyle. Executed within a group setting, SMART entails weekly sessions spanning 90

to 120 minutes over the course of 8 weeks. Notably, the program has achieved noteworthy success among patients grappling with an array of symptoms encompassing chronic pain, fatigue, anxiety, and depression. [23]

Harmony in motion: Therapies rooted in mindful movement:

Among the pantheon of Mind-Body Interventions (MBIs) making notable inroads within community settings, mindful movement-based therapies, including tai chi and yoga, hold a preeminent position. Tai chi, an intricate modality, embodies a multimodal approach encompassing movement, heightened awareness of breath, deliberate breathing exercises, postural alignment and strength training, all coalescing with mindful attention. This practice features methodical, unhurried movements synchronized with breathing patterns or guided by mental imagery, with the overarching aim of fortifying both mental and physical well-being. [24]

While the style and frequency of tai chi practice might vary in community contexts, more standardized interventions tailored for medical and research domains have been formulated. Typically, these interventions entail hour-long sessions administered two to three times per week, extending over the course of 12 weeks. Although a more comprehensive cataloging of adverse events is warranted, existing evidence suggests that tai chi holds a favorable safety profile, even for individuals navigating the complexities of chronic diseases like Parkinson's disease (PD). [25]

The realm of yoga offers a diverse tapestry of practices. Collectively, yoga endeavors to foster a harmonious union between the mind and body, hinging upon the triad of breathing exercises, movement encapsulated within yoga postures, and meditation. The spectrum of yoga practice spans from serene passive stretches (termed as Hatha yoga) to dynamic sequences of yoga postures (embodied by Vinyāsa, Ashtanga), and even to rigorous sequences conducted in

environments heated to exceed 100°F (exemplified by hot yoga or power yoga). A comprehensive meta-analysis, inclusive of randomized controlled trials (RCTs) enlisting various yoga interventions, illuminated yoga's safety equivalence with customary care and conventional exercise. However, this analysis did underscore a marginal increase in intervention-related and non-serious adverse events (though not serious adverse events) vis-à-vis psychological/educational interventions. Intriguingly, nearly 70% of the trials within this meta-analysis refrained from documenting safety data, underscoring the pressing need for more robust safety tracking and comprehensive reporting within the domain of yoga RCTs.

Visualizing Insight: Exploring Mentalizing Imagery Therapy:

Mentalizing denotes the cognitive process through which one comprehends the intricate workings of their own and others' minds, along with the connections these mental processes hold with observable behaviors. This understanding extends even to the complex dynamics of challenging interpersonal scenarios that often either trigger or exacerbate psychological symptoms. Caregivers who tend to individuals grappling with chronic neuropsychiatric conditions frequently encounter the formidable task of mentalizing individuals whose cognitive processes diverge and exhibit diminished cognitive control. A novel intervention named Mentalizing Imagery Therapy (MIT) has recently emerged to address this very challenge. MIT is ingeniously designed to amalgamate the foundational tenets of mentalizing with an array of mindfulness practices and guided imagery techniques, thereby equipping caregivers with tools to impartially observe their own experiences and, in turn, facilitate a more profound understanding of the individuals under their care. [26] Structured across four weekly sessions spanning two hours each, MIT encompasses diverse components like chair yoga, mindfulness exercises, and guided imagery practices.

Unveiling Neurological Disorders: A look at the Supporting Evidence:

Within this segment, we undertake an examination of the empirical substantiation surrounding interventions centering on meditation and mindfulness. Our purview encompasses diverse neurological domains such as headaches, functional neurological disorder (FND), epilepsy, neurodegenerative disorders, movement disorders, stroke, mild cognitive impairment (MCI), and the well-being of caregivers entrusted with individuals grappling with neurological conditions.

Headache:

Recent exploration into mindfulness interventions for treating headaches has yielded a growing body of research. A comprehensive meta-analysis conducted in 2019, encompassing five distinct studies, indicated that Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) did not bring about significant enhancements in the frequency, duration, or intensity of headaches for individuals contending with tension-type and migraine headaches. [27] Despite these initial discouraging findings, two more recent Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs) have presented a more optimistic perspective on the potential benefits of MBSR. The first of these trials, involving 89 adults afflicted by migraines, contrasted MBSR with a control group subjected to headache education. Notably, while both groups exhibited enhancements in the reduction of migraine days, the MBSR group experienced more notable improvements in a range of headache-related aspects encompassing disability, catastrophizing, quality of life, as well as the intensity and discomfort associated with pain. [28] The second study, targeting individuals with episodic migraines, unveiled that when compared with a stress management for headache program, an extended MBSR intervention spanning 12 sessions correlated with greater reductions in headache days and consequent disability at the 20-week mark, albeit not sustaining the same effect at the 52-week point. [29] Thus, while the evidence pertaining to alleviating chronic headaches through

mindfulness meditation remains somewhat nuanced, the recent findings offer a glimmer of promise particularly in the context of migraines. The future trajectory of research in this sphere should strive to refine the specificity of mindfulness interventions for this demographic.

Addressing medication outcomes in the context of headaches, a non-randomized study conducted among 44 subjects grappling with chronic migraine-medication overuse headaches provides notable insights. [30] Participants who successfully navigated a medication withdrawal program were presented with the choice between a prophylactic medication regimen and a six-week group-based mindfulness training. This initiative showcased a reduction in both headache frequency and medication utilization across both groups. Nonetheless, this study did not reveal significant improvements in self-reported anxiety within either group, despite the reduction in catecholamine levels. While randomized trials are warranted for a more comprehensive assessment, this study signifies that mindfulness interventions may potentially yield benefits akin to standardized pharmacological treatments for refractory migraine-medication overuse headaches, particularly for patients who gravitate towards non-pharmacological approaches. A recent meta-analysis, comprising five RCTs, ventured into the domain of yoga as an intervention for headache relief. The findings indicated that yoga may hold the potential to ameliorate headache frequency, duration, and pain intensity within the context of tension headaches, albeit not so distinctly in cases of migraines. [31] However, the quality of the evidence garnered was rated as relatively low, primarily due to methodological constraints. Consequently, this underscores the pressing necessity for further investigations in this sphere to facilitate a more comprehensive understanding of the efficacy of yoga for headache management.

Functional Neurological Disorder:

The application of mindfulness methodologies in addressing Functional Neurological Disorder (FND) has garnered mounting interest. An uncontrolled study conducted among a cohort of individuals (n=98) referred for neurological assessment, inclusive of diverse diagnoses encompassing FND, unveiled a noteworthy correlation between participation in a mindfulness-based intervention and moderate reductions in anxiety and depression levels. [32] Notably, subgroup analysis within this study divulged small-sized effects within the FND subgroup, medium-sized effects among individuals contending with non-progressive neurological conditions, and substantial effects in those afflicted by progressive conditions. Across the board, improvements were observed in the realm of stress management. This intriguing pattern intimates that while mindfulness meditation emerges as a potent tool for stress reduction, augmenting resilience through the active cultivation of coping skills rooted in cognitive strategies, positive psychology, and social support might potentially amplify the therapeutic impact.

Functional (psychogenic nonepileptic/dissociative) seizures (FSs) have increasingly become a focal point of exploration for treatment interventions. Nonetheless, the existing landscape remains scarce in terms of high-quality Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs). In an uncontrolled study by Baslet and colleagues, a mindfulness-based intervention was subjected to scrutiny among individuals contending with FS. Despite notable attrition rates, individuals who persevered and completed the mindfulness intervention showcased enhancements in the frequency, intensity, and overall quality of life concerning FS occurrences. This preliminary endeavor, complemented by a case series presenting parallel findings, offers a glimpse into the feasibility of a mindfulness-oriented approach for individuals wrestling with FS. The outcome

underscores the need for more rigorous investigations to consolidate these promising initial indications.

Epilepsy:

Thompson and collaborators delved into the realm of preventive strategies against Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) through a distance-delivered Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT) group. This investigation particularly focused on individuals grappling with epilepsy and exhibiting mild to moderate depressive symptoms. The outcomes of this study unveiled a markedly lower incidence of MDD episodes (0%) within the MBCT group compared to the treatment as usual group (with an incidence of 10.7%). Furthermore, the MBCT group manifested more pronounced reductions in depressive symptoms on a dimensional scale. Encouragingly, akin effects were observed in the context of web- and telephone-based MBCT iterations. These findings lay the groundwork for the possibility of MBCT in serving as a preventive measure against depressive episodes among individuals navigating epilepsy.

The scope of evidence pertaining to mindful exercise therapies in the context of epilepsy remains comparatively narrower. A Cochrane review, drawing from a modest pool of research, pinpointed merely two studies concerning yoga interventions targeting individuals with epilepsy. Nonetheless, these studies showcased promising outcomes, particularly in terms of seizure outcomes and overall quality of life improvement. [33] Collectively, this underlines the dearth of conclusive data and underscores the exigency for a more expansive research endeavor to gain a more nuanced understanding of the potential of mindful movement therapies for individuals grappling with epilepsy.

Neurodegenerative Disorders:

The landscape of mindfulness interventions within the realm of multiple sclerosis (MS) has witnessed a steady expansion. A pivotal Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) among individuals grappling with MS revealed that, in comparison to treatment as usual, a mindfulness-based intervention yielded notable yet modest reductions in anxiety, depression, and fatigue. Additionally, a substantial enhancement in overall quality of life was observed. [34] These effects demonstrated a commendable resilience at the 6-month follow-up period. Notably, the positive outcomes were particularly conspicuous within the subgroup characterized by more pronounced symptoms, typified by clinical levels of depression, anxiety, and fatigue. A comprehensive meta-analysis conducted in 2019, encompassing 12 RCTs and encompassing a cohort of 744 individuals with MS, traversed the landscape of mindfulness-based interventions vis-à-vis mental well-being. The analysis unveiled a moderate effect size in favor of mindfulness interventions in enhancing overall well-being. Scrutiny of specific outcomes illuminated small to medium effects in the realms of anxiety, depression, and stress reduction. [35] Collectively, these findings furnish a compelling rationale for the potential effectiveness of mindfulness-based interventions in ameliorating common neuropsychiatric symptoms pervasive among individuals navigating MS.

Acknowledging the substantial burden imposed by the disability characteristic of MS, an avenue worth exploring entails the delivery of interventions through distance-based telehealth platforms. [36] An insightful survey conducted in 2015, spanning a participant pool exceeding 2,800 individuals with MS, underscored the considerable unmet psychological needs within this demographic. [37] This serves as a potent reminder of the pressing necessity to bolster the accessibility of psychological services and support mechanisms. Notably, mindfulness-based

interventions administered via telemedicine platforms offer an avenue for promoting health and well-being in patients grappling with neurodegenerative conditions like MS.

Movement Disorders:

Of the various movement disorders, Parkinson's disease (PD) has notably garnered extensive attention in the context of mindfulness-based interventions. A recent systematic review dedicated to the exploration of Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) in PD encompassed a mere three studies. [38] The review showcased that within this limited pool, one study unveiled improvements encompassing PD-related outcomes, depression levels, mindfulness levels, and quality of life. In a separate study, an increase in gray matter density on magnetic resonance imaging was observed subsequent to MBSR, when compared to usual care. While these initial outcomes are undoubtedly promising, the authors of the systematic review tempered their enthusiasm, citing the restricted evidence base fueled by the limited study count, methodological constraints, and a dearth of adverse event reporting. There remains a poignant call for more expansive Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs) offering extended follow-up periods, coupled with rigorous safety monitoring protocols. Stress is renowned for exacerbating motor symptoms, along with neuropsychiatric manifestations such as anxiety and depression, in the context of PD. A comprehensive survey study conducted by Van der Heide and collaborators encompassing a staggering 5,000 individuals with PD and 1,292 control subjects, underscored the heightened perception of stress within the PD cohort as opposed to controls. This stress escalation was associated with a cascade of adverse consequences, spanning heightened rumination, diminished quality of life, decreased self-compassion, deteriorating motor symptoms, and a lower proclivity for dispositional mindfulness. Notably, the practice of mindfulness was adopted by a significant subset of individuals with PD over the preceding three months, although practice frequency

varied (with 53.2% reporting weekly practice and 21.5% engaging in practice less than once a month). Strikingly, PD patients who engaged in mindfulness reported improvements spanning motor parameters (e.g., gait, tremor) and nonmotor realms (e.g., anxiety, depression), with the most pronounced effects manifesting in the realm of anxiety and depressive symptoms. These outcomes shed light on the high acceptability of mindfulness within a substantial PD demographic and provide substantive support for further exploration of mindfulness-based interventions tailored to PD. [39]

A comprehensive meta-analysis conducted in 2019 undertook the task of scrutinizing the effects of both Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) and mindfulness-based interventions across individuals contending with multiple sclerosis (MS), Parkinson's disease (PD), and Huntington's disease (HD). [40] Encompassing a total of 12 studies (8 involving MS and 4 concerning PD), these interventions collectively engendered a notable medium-sized reduction in psychological distress. Within the subset of studies that focused on MS patients, there emerged modest reductions in distress across seven investigations. Notably, no studies were identified that encompassed the HD population. While the positive outcomes evident in the context of MS and PD are noteworthy, the overall quality of the studies was appraised as relatively low, signifying the pressing necessity for more rigorously designed research endeavors in this arena.

Among individuals grappling with PD, the efficacy of tai chi has also undergone scrutiny. A significant Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) involving a cohort of 195 participants showcased tai chi's superiority over resistance training and stretching when it came to improving postural stability. [41] The trial also disclosed tai chi's pronounced impact on enhancing gait, strength, stride length, functional reach (compared to resistance training), and even a reduction in the incidence of falls (in contrast to stretching, though not resistance training). A meta-analysis

conducted in 2017 furnished further insights, suggesting that tai chi was associated with enhancements across diverse domains for individuals with PD. These encompassed motor outcomes, balance, timed walking, falls, depressive symptoms, and quality of life. However, cognition did not exhibit substantial improvement. These cumulative findings underscore the Promising potential of tai chi as an intervention modality for individuals navigating PD. [42]

Post Stroke Recovery:

Mindfulness-based interventions have exhibited potential utility in the post stroke context. A Systematic review conducted in 2013, encompassing four studies and a participant pool of 160, alluded to encouraging trends when it came to the biopsychosocial aftermath of a stroke. The outcomes illuminated favorable shifts in domains spanning anxiety, depression, fatigue, blood Pressure, perceived health, and overall quality of life. [43] Another study delved into the feasibility of a 2-week home-based mindfulness intervention among chronic stroke survivors grappling with spasticity (n=10). Although the study cohort was notably small, the preliminary outcomes offered indications of a reduction in spasticity and an enhancement in quality of life. While the study's diminutive size mandates caution, the findings resonate with the potential of a concise, low-risk, and cost-effective mindfulness intervention capable of yielding holistic benefits encompassing both physical and mental dimensions following a stroke. However, to affirm these preliminary findings, comprehensive and controlled research encompassing larger participant cohorts is essential.

The landscape of mindful movement therapies in the post stroke scenario is equally tantalizing albeit limited. A meta-analysis scrutinizing 19 Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs) suggested that tai chi might engender improvements in balance function and exercise capacity post stroke. [44] A systematic review spanning eight studies traversed the domains of tai chi and yoga,

revealing auspicious trends in terms of ameliorating psychological stressors and bolstering quality of life among poststroke individuals. Notwithstanding these promising trajectories, there emerges a pressing demand for more rigorous and adequately powered RCTs to provide robust evaluation and validation of movement-based therapies in the context of stroke.

Mild Cognitive Impairment:

The landscape of mind-body interventions and their impact on cognition among older adults underwent comprehensive scrutiny in a 2019 meta-analysis encompassing 40 randomized controlled studies, enrolling a total of 3,551 older adult participants. [45] The ambit of mind-body interventions encompassed meditation (embracing mindfulness and other styles), yoga, tai chi, and other mindful movement therapies (such as Qigong). Within this canvas, the meta-analysis illuminated small to moderate effects spanning various cognitive domains. Crucially, these outcomes were underpinned by a low risk of bias. A more nuanced examination revealed that the effect sizes were particularly notable for individuals grappling with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI). The findings unveiled that the effects were notably more pronounced in the context of interventions spanning extended durations (i.e., exceeding 12 weeks), characterized by a session practice frequency of at least three times per week, and featuring sessions lasting a minimum of 45 minutes. Notably, these extended interventions contrast with the relatively shorter interventions typically administered in clinical settings (such as Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction or Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy). Recent studies have ventured into the molecular pathways hypothesized to be mechanistically intertwined with MCI. An intriguing outcome emerged, showcasing sex-specific reductions in C-reactive protein levels among females afflicted with MCI, while males did not manifest the same effect. Conversely, these interventions did not yield any discernible impact on circulating amyloid- β 42 levels. This

delineates a prospect that mindfulness interventions might be more adept at modulating immune activity associated with MCI as opposed to directly impacting amyloid levels. [46]

Caregivers:

The potential of meditative- and mindfulness-focused interventions extends to caregivers of individuals grappling with neurological disorders, offering a glimmer of hope and support in their challenging roles. Evidentiary underpinnings emerge from a recent review that surfaced relatively low-quality evidence, suggesting that Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) could potentially precipitate short-term alleviation of depressive and anxiety symptoms among caregivers tending to those with dementia. [69] Notably, Lavretsky and collaborators ventured into the realm of Kirtan Kriya yoga, a practice entailing around 20 minutes of repetitive mantra chanting coupled with guided imagery. The study unveiled that this particular modality yielded improvements in both depression and executive function among family caregivers of individuals afflicted with dementia. [47] Mentalizing Imagery Therapy (MIT) has also emerged as a feasible and accepted intervention in this context. An empirical exploration juxtaposed MIT against a waitlist control, supplemented with optional relaxation exercises. The caregivers who underwent the MIT intervention exhibited more substantial amelioration in terms of depression and anxiety symptoms, as compared to their waitlist counterparts. Neuroimaging insights divulged augmented connectivity between the dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex (PFC) and an emotion regulation network within the MIT group. In contrast, the waitlist group did not exhibit the same neural changes. In addition to quantitative findings, qualitative exploration brought to the forefront improvements in dimensions spanning well-being, mood, anxiety, and sleep, alongside a newfound ability to perceive themselves more objectively within the complex fabric of challenging relationship situations. [48] However, it is undeniable that these promising

indications necessitate larger-scale randomized controlled trials to substantiate and further explore these interventions' potential efficacy and impact.

Investigating consistent neuropsychiatric phenomena:

In the realm of neuropsychiatric symptoms, meditative- and mindfulness-focused interventions offer a window of promise. This section delves into the evidence supporting their potential efficacy in addressing conditions such as depression, anxiety, chronic pain, and sleep difficulties.

Depression:

Scientific investigation underscores the effectiveness of mindfulness-based interventions in tackling depressive symptoms and preventing relapses of depression. Recent meta-analyses of Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs) have revealed the superiority of these interventions, such as Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT) and Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR), over no treatment and other active therapies. These interventions have been found to be on par with existing evidence-based therapies like Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) for individuals with depression or elevated symptoms. [49] Delving specifically into individuals currently diagnosed with depressive or anxiety disorders, mindfulness interventions showcased a medium-to-large effect in alleviating the severity of depressive symptoms, with MBCT demonstrating particularly notable effects on primary symptom severity. [50]

MBCT has also demonstrated its prowess in curbing the risk of depressive relapses over a 60-week follow-up duration, especially among individuals with recurrent depression in full or partial remission. This impact was pronounced in those exhibiting higher residual symptoms at baseline. [51] Impressively, MBCT stood shoulder to shoulder with active treatments, including antidepressant medication, in terms of effectiveness. This intervention's mechanism of relapse

reduction potentially rests on enhancements in trait mindfulness, reduction in rumination, decentering, worry, and fostering self-compassion. [52]

The SMART program has unveiled its potential in mitigating depressive symptoms across diverse populations. In an open-label study among individuals grappling with Major Depressive Disorder (MDD), SMART facilitated improvements in resilience while concurrently reducing depressive symptoms and perceived stress levels. [53] The domain of yoga and tai chi has also illuminated avenues for alleviating depressive symptoms. [54] In a comprehensive meta-analysis from 2013, yoga exhibited the capacity to diminish depression severity among individuals diagnosed with depressive disorders or elevated symptoms. While the evidence indicated a reduction compared to usual care, the data also hinted at more limited reductions when contrasted with relaxation and aerobic exercise. [55] Tai chi, too, appears to hold potential in reducing depressive symptoms, though there is a prevailing need for more studies of higher quality to comprehensively unravel its impact. [56]

Anxiety:

The landscape of evidence substantiates the efficacy of mindfulness-based interventions in alleviating anxiety symptoms across various conditions. A comprehensive meta-analysis encompassing diverse contexts such as cancer, other medical conditions, and depression revealed a medium-effect size in reducing anxiety symptoms through mindfulness-based interventions. [57] Subsequent analyses echoed this sentiment, showcasing anxiety symptom reduction in healthy adults and individuals grappling with chronic pain conditions like fibromyalgia. However, when examining individuals with anxiety disorders, the evidence presents a more nuanced picture. Vøllestad and associates found that controlled studies pointed to moderate improvement in anxiety symptoms among individuals with anxiety disorders through

mindfulness interventions. [58] Conversely, recent meta-analyses have indicated that while mindfulness-based interventions exhibit superiority over no treatment controls, their effects are akin to other active therapies and evidence-based treatments for individuals with anxiety disorders or elevated symptoms. Notably, a meta-analysis focused on individuals with current anxiety disorders found no significant impact of mindfulness-based interventions on symptom severity.

In pilot trials, the SMART program has demonstrated its potential in ameliorating anxiety symptoms within diverse populations, spanning parents of children with learning and attentional disabilities, breast cancer survivors, and patients with medical conditions like hypertension and neurofibromatosis. [59] Turning to mindful movement-based therapies, research conducted by Cramer and colleagues pinpointed yoga as an avenue for diminishing anxiety symptom severity, particularly when juxtaposed with no treatment or active controls for individuals exhibiting elevated anxiety symptoms. However, the effect appeared less prominent for individuals diagnosed with anxiety disorders according to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM). [60] In a parallel vein, another meta-analysis accentuated yoga's superiority over non-mindful forms of exercise in reducing anxiety symptoms. [61] While the call for more robust Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs) is persistent, there is a burgeoning body of evidence indicating the potential of tai chi in addressing anxiety symptoms.

Chronic Pain:

The body of evidence supporting the efficacy of mindfulness-based interventions (MBIs) for chronic pain-related outcomes is steadily expanding. A comprehensive meta-analysis encompassing individuals with diverse chronic pain conditions, ranging from headaches to fibromyalgia, showcased significant improvements in pain symptoms through MBIs when

compared to treatment as usual, passive controls, and education/support groups. [62]

Nonetheless, the quality of evidence received cautious appraisal due to study heterogeneity and the potential for publication bias. Within this review, analgesic use outcomes were assessed across only four studies, yielding mixed results. Notably, a specific mindfulness intervention, Mindfulness-Oriented Recovery Enhancement, exhibited promise in ameliorating opioid-related outcomes, including misuse risk. [63] A meta-analysis involving individuals grappling with chronic pain conditions underscored that MBIs yield a modest effect on pain intensity and disability, alongside a moderate effect on pain interference compared to waitlist, treatment as usual, and education/support groups. [64] It's intriguing to observe that the neural mechanisms underpinning mindfulness-based pain reduction vary based on the extent of training. Brief training appears linked to reappraisal mechanisms, while longer training is associated with no appraisal – the capacity to differentiate physical pain sensations from the affective and evaluative reactions conventionally associated with pain. [65] Garland and collaborators executed a meta-analysis encompassing a diverse spectrum of MBIs among individuals utilizing opioids for pain management. Across 60 RCTs, MBIs (including meditation, hypnosis, and relaxation) corresponded to reductions in pain symptoms and opioid dosages. Notably, meditation exhibited the most substantial effect size for pain reduction.

Furthermore, the majority of meditation studies reported improvements in opioid-related outcomes such as misuse and cravings. [66] Yoga and tai chi also emerge as potential allies in the management of specific chronic pain conditions. For instance, meta-analyses elucidated the short-term benefits of yoga for neck pain-related outcomes (e.g., pain intensity, disability; n=3 RCTs) and both short- and long-term enhancements in back pain-related outcomes (e.g., pain, disability, global improvement; n=10 RCTs). [67] Tai chi demonstrated potential in yielding

short-term enhancements in pain and disability among individuals contending with musculoskeletal pain conditions. [98] Pertinently, American College of Physician guidelines advocate for MBSR, yoga, and tai chi in addressing chronic low back pain. [68]

Sleep Difficulty:

Theoretical frameworks suggest that mindfulness-based interventions (MBIs) might hold promise in addressing sleep problems by diminishing rumination, arousal, sleep monitoring, effort, and distorted perceptions that often contribute to sleep difficulties. [69] A meta-analysis encompassing 18 randomized controlled trials (RCTs) illuminated the potential of MBIs (such as MBSR and MBCT) in enhancing sleep quality among diverse patient populations grappling with clinically significant sleep issues when compared to active controls. However, such interventions did not exhibit superiority over evidence-based sleep treatments. [70] Furthermore, mindfulness-based interventions seem to have the potential to alleviate insomnia symptoms when compared to placebos and waitlist controls. [71] It is clear that more robust research is necessary to systematically compare mindfulness-based interventions to established evidence-based treatments for sleep problems. Mindful movement-based therapies have demonstrated potential in addressing sleep problems as well. A recent meta-analysis underscored that yoga holds promise in modestly enhancing sleep quality, particularly among women. [72] Another comprehensive meta-analysis, encompassing 22 randomized controlled trials (RCTs), revealed that tai chi exhibited a moderate positive effect on sleep quality among individuals grappling with various conditions and sleep complaints. When compared to both inactive and active controls (such as exercise and health education), tai chi demonstrated its efficacy in promoting improved sleep quality. [73]

Monetary compensation:

Mindfulness-based interventions (MBIs) require a considerable time investment for delivery. The current reimbursement structure poses challenges, as patients may need to cover the cost themselves, which can amount to several hundred dollars per course. This is primarily because there is a lack of well-defined reimbursement mechanisms, especially for providers outside the mental health care domain. Many centers offering MBIs often designate them as out-of-pocket expenses not covered by insurance. This situation creates a significant obstacle, particularly for underserved and marginalized communities with lower socioeconomic status. Access to MBIs becomes a notable challenge in such cases. While certain mindfulness-based interventions are provided by mental health professionals and follow standard referral and insurance reimbursement procedures, there's a growing effort to develop insurance-reimbursable mindfulness programs for delivery in primary care settings to address these issues.

Referral:

Implementing mindfulness-based interventions (MBIs) necessitates a well-organized administrative and referral framework. Adequate administrative support is crucial to facilitate patient navigation and empowerment in clinical services. This need becomes particularly pronounced in the context of chronic neurological conditions, which traditionally have centered on pharmaceutical and procedural treatment approaches. Given that MBIs involve behavioral techniques, patients may pose more inquiries, potentially leading to an increased administrative workload.

Subject variable:

While not an all-encompassing compilation, the following section provides an overview of various patient-specific factors that merit consideration when recommending mindfulness-based interventions (MBIs).

Culture:

The mindfulness-based interventions (MBIs) discussed in this context have their origins in Eastern meditative and spiritual traditions, which might not align with the religious beliefs of certain patients. Although our experience indicates that many patients are receptive to any approach that yields positive results, it's important to engage in thoughtful conversations about the specific practices involved in the MBI. Furthermore, discussions should also address the potential inclusion of cultural elements that stem from traditions such as Buddhism, Hinduism, or Taoism.

Personal Efficacy:

An important cognitive aspect that could be linked to the effectiveness of MBIs is self-efficacy. Self-efficacy pertains to the perceived ease or difficulty of performing a specific behavior. This concept is distinct from controllability, which focuses on the individual's belief in their capacity to influence the execution of the behavior. [74] Self-efficacy plays a role as a mediator in altering health behaviors and utilization of healthcare services. Moreover, self-efficacy has associations with increased vitality, improved sleep, reduced pain, and enhanced overall life satisfaction. [75] In instances where neurobehavioral and physical symptoms present direct challenges to self-efficacy, lowered self-efficacy levels might hinder adherence and consequently impact the effectiveness of the MBI. This situation could potentially create a self-perpetuating negative cycle. Therefore, healthcare providers who recommend or administer MBIs could gain

insight by assessing and comprehending a patient's self-efficacy. This understanding might facilitate participation and active engagement with the MBI.

Cataclysmic thinking:

Cognitive psychological processes may also be important to consider in the context of MBIs.

One specific process, catastrophizing, is often studied in the context of pain and has been shown to be associated with poor pain-related outcomes. [76] Pain catastrophizing refers to the tendency to magnify the threat of pain, ruminate on pain, and feel helpless in regard to pain. Patients with high degrees of catastrophizing may engage in maladaptive behaviors (e.g. avoidance of activity) and experience psychological distress (e.g., depression, anxiety).

Overall, this may magnify symptom intensity and disability, thereby affecting the patient's willingness to participate in an MBI and implement positive health behavior change. Therefore, it may be helpful for providers to assess for levels of catastrophizing, particularly for patients with chronic pain, to better facilitate participation and engagement with a MBI.

Capacity for group environment adaptation:

Given that a significant number of MBIs are conducted in group settings, evaluating the patient's capacity to function effectively within an environment involving close physical proximity to others and potential distractions is crucial. Factors such as visual stimuli from the movements of fellow group participants and unexpected noises can influence this setting. It's important to consider that moderate to severe impairments in memory or attention, as well as behavioral symptoms stemming from diminished inhibition, paranoia, or hallucinations, could intensify when experienced in a group context.

Conclusion:

Meditative- and mindfulness-focused interventions have the potential to alleviate neuropsychiatric symptoms often associated with neurological disorders. Among these interventions, mindfulness-based approaches like MBSR and MBCT have demonstrated the strongest evidence, particularly in preventing depression relapse and reducing symptoms of depression, anxiety, and chronic pain. While mindful movement-based interventions such as yoga and tai chi show promise for addressing common neuropsychiatric symptoms, there is a need for higher quality studies that systematically assess adverse events. Further research is essential to explore the effectiveness of these interventions specifically in neurological populations. When recommending these mind-body therapies, healthcare providers should take into account both structural factors like insurance reimbursement and individual patient considerations, such as their ability to engage in group formats.

References:

- **1** Wahbeh H, Elsas SM, Oken BS. Mind-body interventions: applications in neurology. *Neurology* 2008; 70 (24) 2321-2328

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **2** Farias M, Maraldi E, Wallenkampf KC, Lucchetti G. Adverse events in meditation practices and meditation-based therapies: a systematic review. *Acta Psychiatr Scand* 2020; 142 (05) 374-393

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **3** Walsh R, Shapiro SL. The meeting of meditative disciplines and Western psychology: a mutually enriching dialogue. *Am Psychol* 2006; 61 (03) 227-239

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **4** Bishop SR, Lau M, Shapiro S. et al. Mindfulness: a proposed operational definition. Clin Psychol (New York) 2004; 11: 230-241

[PubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **5** Lau MA, Bishop SR, Segal ZV. et al. The Toronto Mindfulness Scale: development and validation. J Clin Psychol 2006; 62 (12) 1445-1467

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **6** Zeidan F, Salomons T, Farris SR. et al. Neural mechanisms supporting the relationship between dispositional mindfulness and pain. Pain 2018; 159 (12) 2477-2485

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **7** Fledderus M, Bohlmeijer ET, Pieterse ME, Schreurs KM. Acceptance and commitment therapy as guided self-help for psychological distress and positive mental health: a randomized controlled trial. Psychol Med 2012; 42 (03) 485-495

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **8** Kang Y, Gruber J, Gray JR. Mindfulness and de-automatization. Emot Rev 2013; 5: 192-201

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **9** Hayes SC. Acceptance and commitment therapy, relational frame theory, and the third wave of behavioral and cognitive therapies - republished article. Behav Ther 2016; 47 (06) 869-885

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **10** Sauer S, Baer RA. Mindfulness and decentering as mechanisms of change in mindfulness-and acceptance-based interventions. In: Baer RA. ed. Assessing Mindfulness and Acceptance Processes in Clients. Oakland: Context Press; 2010: 25-50

[Google Scholar](#)

- **11** Levin ME, Luoma JB, Haeger JA. Decoupling as a mechanism of change in mindfulness and acceptance: a literature review. Behav Modif 2015; 39 (06) 870-911

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **12** Vago DR, Silbersweig DA. Self-awareness, self-regulation, and self-transcendence (S-ART): a framework for understanding the neurobiological mechanisms of mindfulness. Front Hum Neurosci 2012; 6: 296

[PubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **13** Chiesa A, Calati R, Serretti A. Does mindfulness training improve cognitive abilities? A systematic review of neuropsychological findings. Clin Psychol Rev 2011; 31 (03) 449-464

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **14** Guendelman S, Medeiros S, Rampes H. Mindfulness and emotion regulation: Insights from neurobiological, psychological, and clinical studies. *Front Psychol* 2017; 8: 220

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **15** Chen WG, Schloesser D, Arensdorf AM. et al. The emerging science of interoception: sensing, integrating, interpreting, and regulating signals within the self. *Trends Neurosci* 2021; 44 (01) 3-16

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **16** Farb N, Daubenmier J, Price CJ. et al. Interoception, contemplative practice, and health. *Front Psychol* 2015; 6: 763

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **17** Mennin DS, Fresco DM. What, me worry and ruminate about DSM-5 and RDoC? The importance of targeting negative self-referential processing. *Clin Psychol (New York)* 2013; 20 (03) 258-267

[PubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **18** Kabat-Zinn J. *Wherever You Go, There You Are: Mindfulness Meditation in Everyday Life*. 1st ed.. New York, NY: Hyperion; 1994

[Google Scholar](#)

- **19** Segal ZV, Williams JMG, Teasdale J. Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy for Depression: a New Approach to Preventing Relapse. New York, NY: Guilford Press; 2002

[Google Scholar](#)

- **20** Grossman P, Niemann L, Schmidt S, Walach H. Mindfulness-based stress reduction and health benefits. A meta-analysis. J Psychosom Res 2004; 57 (01) 35-43

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **21** Garland EL, Manusov EG, Froeliger B, Kelly A, Williams JM, Howard MO. Mindfulness-oriented recovery enhancement for chronic pain and prescription opioid misuse: results from an early-stage randomized controlled trial. J Consult Clin Psychol 2014; 82 (03) 448-459

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **22** Park ER, Traeger L, Vranceanu AM. et al. The development of a patient-centered program based on the relaxation response: the Relaxation Response Resiliency Program (3RP). Psychosomatics 2013; 54 (02) 165-174

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **23** Dossett ML, Fricchione GL, Benson H. A new era for mind-body medicine. N Engl J Med 2020; 382 (15) 1390-1391

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **24** Wayne PM, Kaptchuk TJ. Challenges inherent to t'ai chi research: part I—t'ai chi as a complex multicomponent intervention. *J Altern Complement Med* 2008; 14 (01) 95-102

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **25** Ni X, Liu S, Lu F, Shi X, Guo X. Efficacy and safety of Tai Chi for Parkinson's disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *PLoS One* 2014; 9 (06) e99377

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **26** Jain FA, Fonagy P. Mentalizing imagery therapy: theory and case series of imagery and mindfulness techniques to understand self and others. *Mindfulness (N Y)* 2020; 11 (01) 153-165

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **27** Anheyer D, Leach MJ, Klose P, Dobos G, Cramer H. Mindfulness-based stress reduction for treating chronic headache: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Cephalalgia* 2019; 39 (04) 544-555

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **28** Wells RE, O'Connell N, Pierce CR. et al. Effectiveness of mindfulness meditation vs headache education for adults with migraine: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA Intern Med* 2021; 181 (03) 317-328

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **29** Seminowicz DA, Burrowes SAB, Kearson A. et al. Enhanced mindfulness-based stress reduction in episodic migraine: a randomized clinical trial with magnetic resonance imaging outcomes. *Pain* 2020; 161 (08) 1837-1846

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **30** Grazzi L, Raggi A, D'Amico D. et al. A prospective pilot study of the effect on catecholamines of mindfulness training vs pharmacological prophylaxis in patients with chronic migraine and medication overuse headache. *Cephalalgia* 2019; 39 (05) 655-664

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **31** Anheyer D, Klose P, Lauche R, Saha FJ, Cramer H. Yoga for treating headaches: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Gen Intern Med* 2020; 35 (03) 846-854

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **32** Detert NB, Douglass L. Mindfulness MBSR/MBCT in a UK public health neurological service: depression, anxiety, and perceived stress outcomes in a heterogeneous clinical sample of ninety-eight patients with neurological or functional disorders. *Neurodisabil Psychother* 2014; 2: 137-156

[PubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **33** Panjwani U, Selvamurthy W, Singh SH, Gupta HL, Thakur L, Rai UC. Effect of Sahaja yoga practice on seizure control & EEG changes in patients of epilepsy. *Indian J Med Res* 1996; 103: 165-172

[PubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **34** Grossman P, Kappos L, Gensicke H. et al. MS quality of life, depression, and fatigue improve after mindfulness training: a randomized trial. *Neurology* 2010; 75 (13) 1141-1149

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **35** Simpson R, Simpson S, Ramparsad N, Lawrence M, Booth J, Mercer SW. Mindfulness-based interventions for mental well-being among people with multiple sclerosis: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry* 2019; 90 (09) 1051-1058

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **36** Ehde DM, Elzea JL, Verrall AM, Gibbons LE, Smith AE, Amtmann D. Efficacy of a telephone-delivered self-management intervention for persons with multiple sclerosis: a randomized controlled trial with a one-year follow-up. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil* 2015; 96 (11) 1945.e2-1958.e2

[PubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **37** McCabe MP, Ebacioni KJ, Simmons R, McDonald E, Melton L. Unmet education, psychological and peer support needs of people with multiple sclerosis. *J Psychosom Res* 2015; 78 (01) 82-87

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **38** McLean G, Lawrence M, Simpson R, Mercer SW. Mindfulness-based stress reduction in Parkinson's disease: a systematic review. BMC Neurol 2017; 17 (01) 92

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **39** van der Heide A, Speckens AEM, Meinders MJ, Rosenthal LS, Bloem BR, Helmich RC. Stress and mindfulness in Parkinson's disease - a survey in 5000 patients. NPJ Parkinsons Dis 2021; 7 (01) 7

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **40** Ghielen I, Rutten S, Boeschoten RE. et al. The effects of cognitive behavioral and mindfulness-based therapies on psychological distress in patients with multiple sclerosis, Parkinson's disease and Huntington's disease: Two meta-analyses. J Psychosom Res 2019; 122: 43-51

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **41** Li F, Harmer P, Fitzgerald K. et al. Tai chi and postural stability in patients with Parkinson's disease. N Engl J Med 2012; 366 (06) 511-519

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **42** Song R, Grabowska W, Park M. et al. The impact of Tai Chi and Qigong mind-body exercises on motor and non-motor function and quality of life in Parkinson's disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis. Parkinsonism Relat Disord 2017; 41: 3-13

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **43** Lawrence M, Booth J, Mercer S, Crawford E. A systematic review of the benefits of mindfulness-based interventions following transient ischemic attack and stroke. *Int J Stroke* 2013; 8 (06) 465-474

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **44** Zheng X, Wu X, Liu Z. et al. The influences of tai chi on balance function and exercise capacity among stroke patients: a meta-analysis. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med* 2021; 2021: 6636847

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **45** Chan JSY, Deng K, Wu J, Yan JH. Effects of meditation and mind–body exercises on older adults' cognitive performance: a meta-analysis. *Gerontologist* 2019; 59 (06) e782-e790

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **46** Ng TKS, Slowey PD, Beltran D, Ho RCM, Kua EH, Mahendran R. Effect of mindfulness intervention versus health education program on salivary A β -42 levels in community-dwelling older adults with mild cognitive impairment: a randomized controlled trial. *J Psychiatr Res* 2021; 136: 619-625

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **47** Lavretsky H, Epel ES, Siddarth P. et al. A pilot study of yogic meditation for family dementia caregivers with depressive symptoms: effects on mental health, cognition, and telomerase activity. *Int J Geriatr Psychiatry* 2013; 28 (01) 57-65

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **48** Yang FC, Zamaria J, Morgan S. et al. How family dementia caregivers perceive benefits of a 4-week MIT mindfulness and guided imagery program: a pilot study. *Prof Psychol Res Pract* In press

[Google Scholar](#)

- **49** Goldberg SB, Tucker RP, Greene PA. et al. Mindfulness-based interventions for psychiatric disorders: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clin Psychol Rev* 2018; 59: 52-60

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **50** Strauss C, Cavanagh K, Oliver A, Pettman D. Mindfulness-based interventions for people diagnosed with a current episode of an anxiety or depressive disorder: a meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials. *PLoS One* 2014; 9 (04) e96110

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **51** Kuyken W, Warren FC, Taylor RS. et al. Efficacy of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy in prevention of depressive relapse: an individual patient data meta-analysis from randomized trials. *JAMA Psychiatry* 2016; 73 (06) 565-574

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **52** van der Velden AM, Kuyken W, Wattar U. et al. A systematic review of mechanisms of change in mindfulness-based cognitive therapy in the treatment of recurrent major depressive disorder. Clin Psychol Rev 2015; 37: 26-39

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **53** Seshadri A, Clark MM, Kung S. et al. Feasibility study of stress management and resiliency training (SMART) in patients with major depressive disorder. Prim Care Companion CNS Disord 2020; 22 (03) 19

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **54** Jain FA, Walsh RN, Eisendrath SJ, Christensen S, Rael Cahn B. Critical analysis of the efficacy of meditation therapies for acute and subacute phase treatment of depressive disorders: a systematic review. Psychosomatics 2015; 56 (02) 140-152

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **55** Cramer H, Lauche R, Langhorst J, Dobos G. Yoga for depression: a systematic review and meta-analysis. Depress Anxiety 2013; 30 (11) 1068-1083

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **56** Wang F, Lee EK, Wu T. et al. The effects of tai chi on depression, anxiety, and psychological well-being: a systematic review and meta-analysis. Int J Behav Med 2014; 21 (04) 605-617

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **57** Hofmann SG, Sawyer AT, Witt AA, Oh D. The effect of mindfulness-based therapy on anxiety and depression: a meta-analytic review. *J Consult Clin Psychol* 2010; 78 (02) 169-183

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **58** Vøllestad J, Nielsen MB, Nielsen GH. Mindfulness- and acceptance-based interventions for anxiety disorders: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Br J Clin Psychol* 2012; 51 (03) 239-260

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **59** Bhasin MK, Denninger JW, Huffman JC. et al. Specific transcriptome changes associated with blood pressure reduction in hypertensive patients after relaxation response training. *J Altern Complement Med* 2018; 24 (05) 486-504

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **60** Cramer H, Lauche R, Anheyer D. et al. Yoga for anxiety: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Depress Anxiety* 2018; 35 (09) 830-843

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **61** So WWY, Lu EY, Cheung WM, Tsang HWH. Comparing mindful and non-mindful exercises on alleviating anxiety symptoms: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 2020; 17 (22) 8692

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **62** Hilton L, Hempel S, Ewing BA. et al. Mindfulness meditation for chronic pain: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Ann Behav Med* 2017; 51 (02) 199-213

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **63** Garland EL, Hanley AW, Riquino MR. et al. Mindfulness-oriented recovery enhancement reduces opioid misuse risk via analgesic and positive psychological mechanisms: a randomized controlled trial. *J Consult Clin Psychol* 2019; 87 (10) 927-940

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **64** Veehof MM, Trompetter HR, Bohlmeijer ET, Schreurs KM. Acceptance- and mindfulness-based interventions for the treatment of chronic pain: a meta-analytic review. *Cogn Behav Ther* 2016; 45 (01) 5-31

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **65** Jinich-Diamant A, Garland E, Baumgartner J. et al. Neurophysiological mechanisms supporting mindfulness meditation-based pain relief: an updated review. *Curr Pain Headache Rep* 2020; 24 (10) 56

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **66** Garland EL, Brintz CE, Hanley AW. et al. Mind-body therapies for opioid-treated pain: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *JAMA Intern Med* 2020; 180 (01) 91-105

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **67** Cramer H, Lauche R, Haller H, Dobos G. A systematic review and meta-analysis of yoga for low back pain. Clin J Pain 2013; 29 (05) 450-460

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **68** Hall A, Copsey B, Richmond H. et al. Effectiveness of tai chi for chronic musculoskeletal pain conditions: updated systematic review and meta-analysis. Phys Ther 2017; 97 (02) 227-238

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **69** Shallcross AJ, Visvanathan PD, Sperber SH, Duberstein ZT. Waking up to the problem of sleep: can mindfulness help? A review of theory and evidence for the effects of mindfulness for sleep. Curr Opin Psychol 2019; 28: 37-41

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **70** Rusch HL, Rosario M, Levison LM. et al. The effect of mindfulness meditation on sleep quality: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. Ann N Y Acad Sci 2019; 1445 (01) 5-16

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **71** Wang YY, Wang F, Zheng W. et al. Mindfulness-based interventions for insomnia: a meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. Behav Sleep Med 2020; 18 (01) 1-9

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **72** Wang WL, Chen KH, Pan YC, Yang SN, Chan YY. The effect of yoga on sleep quality and insomnia in women with sleep problems: a systematic review and meta-analysis. BMC Psychiatry 2020; 20 (01) 195

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **73** Li H, Chen J, Xu G. et al. The effect of tai chi for improving sleep quality: a systematic review and meta-analysis. J Affect Disord 2020; 274: 1102-1112

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **74** Ajzen I. Perceived behavioral control, self-efficacy, locus of control, and the theory of planned behavior 1. J Appl Soc Psychol 2002; 32: 665-683

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **75** Scult M, Haime V, Jacquart J. et al. A healthy aging program for older adults: effects on self-efficacy and morale. Adv Mind Body Med 2015; 29 (01) 26-33

[PubMedGoogle Scholar](#)

- **76** Quartana PJ, Campbell CM, Edwards RR. Pain catastrophizing: a critical review. Expert Rev Neurother 2009; 9 (05) 745-758

[CrossrefPubMedGoogle Scholar](#)